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"DESCRIPTION OF COMPLIANCE WITH THE CONSUMPTION OF YELLOW SEED CAPSULES (*CURCUBITA MOSCHATA DUCH*) IN PREDIABETES PATIENTS IN JUMPANDANG BARU HEALTH CENTRE MAKASSAR CITY"

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Medication adherence in prediabetes patients is one of the ways to keep blood glucose within normal limits. **Objective:** This study aims to determine the description of compliance with taking pumpkin seed capsules (*Curcubita moschata Duch*) in patients with prediabetes in the Jumpandang Baru health centre area in Makassar city. **Materials and Methods:** This study is a descriptive study with a sample size of 37 people. Data collection in this study was to use a family support questionnaire, a knowledge level questionnaire along with a monitoring sheet for drug compliance schedule. Data analysis in this study used univariate analysis using the frequency test on SPSS. **Results:** In the characteristics of 37 respondents, the age of the most respondents was 51-60 years old (35.1%), the last level of education of the most respondents was high school (51.4%), the occupation of the most respondents was housewife (78.4%), and the marital status of the respondents was married status (78.4%) and widow status (21.8%). In the results of univariate analysis, based on the level of adherence to taking medication, most prediabetic women are in the high category (89.2%). Based on the statement of family support for prediabetic women is the respondent's family hears what complaints are experienced. Based on respondents who answered correctly on the statement of general knowledge of diabetes is the time to take pumpkin seed capsules and the dose in taking pumpkin seed capsules (100%). Based on the level of knowledge of prediabetes, most of them were in the high category (64.9%). **Conclusion:** The high adherence to taking medication in this study was due to the desire to recover from oneself and the family who played an active role while the respondents were taking medication and good knowledge in the respondents.

Keywords: Prediabetes, Pumpkin Seed Capsules, Medication Adherence.

INTRODUCTION:

The current and future epidemiological transition of diseases in society tends to shift from infectious diseases to non-communicable diseases. WHO 2020 reported that the number of people with diabetes increased from 108 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014. In 2016, an estimated 1.6 million deaths were directly attributable to diabetes then another 2.2 million deaths were attributable to high blood glucose in 2012¹.

According to the 2018 Riskesdas, the prevalence of diabetes mellitus in women is higher at 1.78% compared to men at 1.21%. In the South Sulawesi region, diabetes mellitus ranks third highest as a non-communicable disease, after heart and blood vessel disease (PJPD) with a rate of 15.79% in 2017. According to the South Sulawesi Provincial Health Profile, Puskesmas Jumpandang Baru is one of the health centres with the highest incidence rate with a total incidence of diabetes cases in three consecutive years, namely in 2018 of 342 cases, 2019 of 725 cases and in 2020 of 955 cases².

One of the efforts to overcome the development of prediabetes can be done by routinely taking medication, but in the medical world, there are several drugs with certain chemical content and cause side effects if consumed not as recommended, which will have an impact on organ damage. In addition, one of the alternative treatments that can be an option to reduce glucose levels in the blood is herbal therapy. Herbal therapy is a complementary therapy using plants that are efficacious as herbal medicines, one of which is pumpkin seeds.³

Pumpkin is a plant that has been scientifically proven to control blood sugar in diabetes mellitus⁴. Pumpkin seeds contain natural antioxidants such as flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, kukurbitasin, lecithin, resin, stearin, phytosterol compounds, phenolics, fatty acids, squalen, tyrosol, vanillic acid, vanillin, luteolin and sinapat acid, vitamins (including vitamin β -carotene, vitamin A, vitamin B2, α -tocopherol, vitamin C and vitamin E⁵). Antioxidants in pumpkin seeds can be needed by the body to overcome and prevent oxidative stress in patients with diabetes mellitus⁶. Previous research conducted by (Sharma et.al 2013) which showed that oral administration of pumpkin seed extract in diabetic model rats can control blood glucose to normal⁷. One form of product development from pumpkin seeds is pumpkin seed capsules.

One of the determinants of success in prediabetes treatment is medication adherence. Adherent consumption of pumpkin seed capsules can reduce the risk of diabetes mellitus. Prediabetes patients need support from the closest people, especially family, who can remind them to take medicine. In addition to support from the family, knowledge is also very influential in terms of taking medicine, this is because patients who have low knowledge of health tend to often ignore instructions and consider diabetes a disease that is not so fatal. Based on previous research conducted by Elda Nazriati et.al, it is stated that there is a relationship between knowledge in compliance with taking medication in patients with diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.022$)⁹. From this description, the researcher intends to examine the description of compliance with taking pumpkin seed capsules (*Curcubita moschata Duch*) in patients with prediabetes in the Jumpandang Baru health centre area in Makassar city.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This type of research is a type of quantitative research with a descriptive study approach. This research is part of the umbrella research of S3 students on behalf of Zhasnaz Tasya SKM., M.Kes with the title "Study of the Efficacy of Pumpkin Seed Capsule Intervention with *Mindfulness Basic Cognitife Therapy* on the Quality of Life of Prediabetes Mellitus Patients". Data collection was carried out using

a checklist sheet for drug compliance and univariate descriptive analysis using SPSS and data presentation was carried out in the form of tables and narratives.

The location of this study was in the working area of Jumpondang Baru Health Centre, Makassar city. The population in this study were all prediabetes patients who had passed the previous *screening* process, while the sample size in this study was all of the prediabetes patients who received pumpkin seed capsule intervention at Jumpondang Baru health centre, namely 37 people with sampling in this study was by total sampling. In this study, what was used as a data collection tool was a questionnaire in the form of family support, a questionnaire on the level of knowledge about diabetes, and a monitoring sheet for drug compliance schedules.

To measure the respondents' medication adherence, an interview was conducted by asking how many times they took the medicine in a month and also asking the reason why the patient did not take the medicine. The results of the drug compliance questionnaire were divided into two categories, namely low (taking ≤ 48 drugs) and high (taking > 48 drugs)⁹. The results of the family support questionnaire were divided into two categories, namely supportive (respondents' answers scored ≤ 10) and unsupportive (respondents' answers scored > 10)¹⁰. To measure the level of knowledge, an interview was conducted using a knowledge questionnaire about pumpkin seed capsules, where the results of the questionnaire were divided into 2 categories, namely low (score obtained ≤ 4) and high (score obtained > 4). Meanwhile, to measure monitoring in 2 ways, namely the first patient comes to the gathering point and is asked directly regarding the consumption of pumpkin seed capsules and the second way if the respondent does not come to the gathering point the researcher visits the respondent's house or asks about the consumption of pumpkin seed capsules via *Whatsapp*.

RESULTS

The subjects in this study were prediabetic women aged > 45 years who lived in the Jumpondang Baru health centre area of Makassar city with the highest age group being 45-55 years old (40.5%), while the lowest age was > 75 years old (5.4%). at the last level of education the most respondents were high school (51.4%), while the last education of the few respondents was D3 education (5.4%). The occupation of most respondents was housewife (78.4%), while the occupation of the few respondents was trader (21.8%). The marital status of most respondents was married (78.4%), while the marital status of the fewest respondents was widowed (21.8%) (Table 1).

Table 1. General Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristics of respondents	Number of Respondents	
	n	%
Age Group		
45-55	15	40,5
56-65	13	35,1
66-75	7	18,9
>75	2	5,4
Education Level		
Finished primary school	11	29,7

Completed junior high school	5	13,5
Completed high school	19	51,4
College Graduate (D3)	2	5,4
Jobs		
Housewife	29	78,4
Merchants	8	21,6
Marital Status		
Married	29	78,4
Widows	8	21,6
Total	37	100,0

Source: Primary Data, 2021

Table 5.1 shows that most of the prediabetic women were in the age group of 45-55 years, namely 15 people with a percentage (40.5%) and the least age category was 2 people aged > 75 years (5.4%). In addition, the total sample of 37 people with the highest education level category was at the high school education level as many as 19 people with a percentage (51.4%) and the least at the D3 education level as many as 2 people (5.4%). The majority of prediabetic women who do not work are 29 people (78.4%), meaning that most prediabetic women are housewives, while women who work as traders are 8 people (21.8%). The marital status of the respondents showed that 29 people were married with a percentage (78.4%) and 8 people (21.8%) were widowed.

Table. 2 Frequency Distribution of Prediabetic Women Based on Family Support

Family Support	n	%
Support	26	70,2
Not in favour	11	29,8
Total	37	100

Source: Primary Data, 2021

Based on table 5.5, the respondents showed that the distribution of prediabetic women based on family support showed that the family with a supportive category in taking medication was 26 people (70.2%) and the family with a non-supportive category was 11 people (26.8%).

Table. 3 Frequency Distribution of Patient Knowledge Level

No.	Description	Correct		Wrong	
		n	%	n	%
1	Prediabetes can be reversed...	37	100	0	0.0
2	The following are early signs of diabetes except...	27	73.0	10	27
3	Some of the ways to prevent prediabetes from progressing to diabetes are....	35	96.6	2	5.4
4	The following are the types of foods recommended for people with prediabetes, except...	21	56.8	16	43.2
5	Apart from lowering blood glucose, here are some benefits of pumpkin seed capsules, except ...	25	67.6	12	32.4

6	The time to take pumpkin seed capsules is... How many pumpkin seed capsules a day	37	100	0	0.0
7	should be consumed and when should they be taken?	37	100	0	0.0

Source: Primary Data, 2021

Table 3 shows that based on prediabetes knowledge questions that many respondents answered correctly were about the time to take pumpkin seed capsules and the dose in taking pumpkin seed capsules, namely 37 people (100%), while prediabetes knowledge questions that many respondents answered incorrectly were the types of food recommended for prediabetes patients, namely 21 people (56.8%).

Table. 4 Frequency of Adherence to Taking Patient Medication and Distribution of Respondents' Answers Based on the Level of Knowledge of Prediabetic Women at Jumpandang Baru Health Centre

Medication Adherence	n	%
Compliant	33	89.2
Non-compliant	4	10.8
Knowledge level of prediabetic women	n	%
High	24	64.9
Low	13	35.1
Total	37	100.0

Source: Primary Data, 2021

Table 4 shows that most of the respondents were classified as high (89.2%) in compliance in consuming pumpkin seed capsules, while respondents who were classified as low in compliance in consuming pumpkin seed capsules were 10.8%. The level of knowledge of prediabetic women is mostly high category (64.9%), while the level of knowledge of prediabetic women is low category (35.1%).

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the study of 37 respondents (table 4), it shows that most in the Jumpandang Baru health centre area of Makassar city have high compliance in consuming pumpkin seed capsules (89.2%) and most respondents have high knowledge about prediabetes (64.9%).

The results of the study of drug compliance are in line with research conducted by Nanda et al (2018) which states that drug compliance affects the regulation of blood sugar levels in patients with diabetes mellitus. The risk analysis obtained an OR value of 14 with 95% CI (1.385-141.485), which means that respondents who are not obedient to taking anti-diabetic drugs are at risk of 14 times experiencing uncontrolled blood sugar regulation compared to respondents who are obedient to taking anti-diabetic drugs. The *odds ratio* value shows that the more compliant the patient is in taking anti-diabetic drugs, the more controlled the blood sugar will be, but if the patient is not compliant in taking anti-diabetic drugs then the opposite, the blood sugar becomes uncontrolled¹¹. The results of the level of knowledge of prediabetes women in this study are in line with research conducted by Firda, et al (2015) showing that most respondents with good knowledge have good compliance (64.2%)¹².

According to the researcher's assumption, compliance with consuming pumpkin seed capsules in prediabetic women in the Jumpandang Baru health centre area in Makassar city is mostly in the high category. In this study, the largest percentage of respondents' age characteristics (table 1) was in the

51-60 years age group, namely 13 people (35.1%), where at that age, the respondents' work was not too much and several studies mentioned that a person pays more attention to his health at an age entering old age, one of which is by taking medicine obediently. According to WHO, after the age of 30 years, fasting blood glucose levels will increase by 1-2 mg/dL/year and blood sugar at 2 hours after eating will increase by 5.5-13 mg/dL. The age results in this study are in line with research conducted by Desi et al (2018) which states that patients with diabetes mellitus who were first diagnosed with diabetes mellitus at the age of ≥ 45 years were higher than respondents who were first diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus at the age of < 45 ¹³.

The highest number of respondents' education was in senior high school (35.1%). A higher level of education will make it easier for a person or community to absorb information and implement it in their daily behaviour and lifestyle, especially in complying with DM diet management¹⁴. This study is in line with research conducted by Retnowati and Satyabakti (2015) which states that most of the education of Diabetes Mellitus patients (33.3%) has completed high school / equivalent education¹⁵. In addition to the latest education, work can be a factor in compliance with taking pumpkin seed capsules in prediabetic women. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the most respondents' occupations are housewives (78.4%). According to Palimbunga, et al (2017) a person's job affects their physical activity. non-working groups tend to do less physical activity so that there is no movement of the limbs, this results in it being easier to experience DM disease¹⁶.

The majority of respondents' marital status was married (78.4%). The basis of prediabetes is insulin resistance which can occur in muscle, liver, and fat tissue. Some factors that influence the occurrence of insulin resistance in prediabetes are genetics, obesity, gender, and lifestyle¹⁷. The results of this study are similar to those conducted by Diana Rian *et al* (2013) which showed the results that married women have a risk of almost 3 times higher to experience obesity than women who are not married¹⁸.

The results (table 2) of 37 respondents, show that family support is good from the aspects of informational support, emotional support, assessment support and instrumental support. According to Friedman (2010), family support is the attitude, action, and acceptance of the family towards the patient¹⁹. Family support in diabetic patients is expected to help the successful management of diabetes, so as to avoid complications and improve the quality of life of diabetic patients²⁰.

CONCLUSIONS

Characteristics of prediabetic women with a total of 37 respondents. The majority of respondents were in the age group 45-55 years, as many as 15 respondents (40.5%), most of the respondents were in the last high school / equivalent education group as many as 19 people (51.4%). While the type of work group of housewives was 29 people (78.4%). And in the marital status group, 29 respondents were married (78.4%). In addition, most of the respondents as many as 33 people (89.2%) obeyed taking pumpkin seed capsule medicine. Family support from all respondents 26 people (70.2%) had family support in the supportive category. Most of the respondents had high knowledge as many as 24 people (64.9%). And for prediabetes patients to improve their compliance in taking pumpkin seed capsules because based on the results of the study as many as 4 respondents (10.8%) were still not obedient in taking pumpkin seed capsules.

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